

Liberation of Gas in the Non-electrodeic Region During Electrolysis

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During our already reported^{1,2} experiments on electrolysis accompanied by electrode glow, we often observed gas evolution in the intermediate zone. Since this is impossible to happen according to the existing well accepted concept of electrolysis, which allows ions to be discharged and liberated on the electrodes only, we have carefully investigated the matter and have confirmed that gases can get liberated in the intermediate zone though the main bulk of course gets liberated on the electrodes; this note is a preliminary report of the same.

EXPERIMENTAL

FIG. 1

1. S. R. Palit, *Indian J. Phys.* 1967, **41**, 622.
2. S. R. Palit, *Indian J. Phys.* 1967, **41**, 860.

A simple experimental set-up as shown in fig. 1 is used. The two beakers along with the bridge-tube T and the gas burette B (fig. 1a) are filled with the electrolyte under study. A current is sent through the two bright platinum wire electrodes from the 220 volts D.C. mains. A rheostat or an electric bulb is included in the circuit in series to adjust the initial current and to prevent too high an increase of current which may lead to intense heating and/or electrode glow. According to the present concept of electrolysis the gases are expected to be liberated on the electrodes and to escape into the atmosphere and nothing is expected to collect in the bridge-tube T or in the gas burette, B. What is observed is however quite different. Taking for example, potassium nitrate solution (0.2 N) as the electrolyte and a 40 watt bulb in series as the current regulator, the following is observed. The current is observed to rise slowly with time, and after a few hours bubbles start forming in the intermediate zone and collecting in the gas burette, B. The gas burette B (5 ml) becomes full in the course of the next six hours or so after the gas starts collecting. Almost all electrolytes behave more or less in a similar manner but most of our experiments have been carried out with potassium nitrate solution (0.2 N) as it produces the intermediate zone gas (to be called IZ gas for brevity) much faster than most others under comparable conditions. The following are some other features connected with the above remarkable observation.

(i) The current increases with time reaches a maximum sometime after the IZ gas evolution in T starts and then slowly falls to a very low value.

(ii) The catholyte becomes much hotter sometime by as high as 10° or so than the anolyte when the IZ gas evolution starts. The centre of the bridge tube often feels to touch like a very hot spot.

(iii) The production rate and yield of IZ gas depend on the potential drop, the value of the controlling resistance, the current strength and the size of the bridge tube, and the optimum condition is found out by trial and error.

(iv) The gas which collects in the gas burette B, is found to be almost wholly of oxygen ($\sim 90\%$) in most cases, though it has been found to be as low as about sixty per cent in some cases.

DISCUSSION

The basic factual question is whether the gas is truly liberated in the intermediate zone or on the electrodes. The following points clearly show that the gases collecting in B do not come from the electrodes. Firstly, if they had originated on the electrodes they should have started collecting right from the beginning of electrolysis; however they start collecting only after a few hours, often as high as six to twelve hours. In some cases there is hardly any IZ gas liberation. Secondly, if the cathode and the anode are both put separately in two cellophane sacs to prevent any possible gas diffusion, the formation of gas in T and collection in B is not at all hampered; in fact, the process is much accelerated. Thirdly, if a set-up as shown in Fig. 1b is used, it is observed using potassium nitrate (0.2N) that most of the intermediate zone gas collects in the middle bridge-tube, B₂. This conclusively shows that the electrodes have nothing to do with IZ gas.

Before we suggest any explanation it is to be noted that the current-time characteristic of this system is somewhat similar to the current-time behaviour of our glowing electrode system^{1,2}, viz. a steady rise of the current value with time is followed by a rather steep fall, except that the fall here is not so sudden as in the former.

The explanation may be basically similar in the two cases. We think that current produces charged water molecules, $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{\text{aq}}^+$ and $(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{\text{aq}}^-$ at the anode and the cathode respectively which for simplicity we shall represent as H_2O^+ and H_2O^- . These ion radicals migrate either bodily or by a Grothus-type chain relay mechanism and the intermediate zone gases are formed by the reaction of these ion radicals with suitable ions of opposite charge or by their self-decomposition. These ion radicals slowly build up in the system which increases the conductivity of the system. The subsequent fall of current may be due to increasing exhaustion of the electrolyte inside the bridge-tube T.

Our surmise is that some H_2O^+ ion radicals are formed near the anode and move towards the cathode. In their path they meet anions particularly OH^- ions and react with the latter (eqn i) to form oxygen which gets liberated in the intermediate zone. Self decomposition may also take place (eqn ii). A similar behaviour is also expected of the H_2O^- ion radicals, i.e., hydrated electrons which form near the cathode. However, they are probably much more reactive³ and so they either react with the protons or decompose mostly in regions near to the cathode (eqns iii and iv) and so very few of such ion radicals get a chance to migrate further away to the intermediate zone. This is probably the reason of the overwhelming percentage of oxygen in the IZ gas.

Consistent with the above concept sodium hydroxide solution shows very little intermediate zone electrolysis under comparable conditions and that only in gas burette B₁ (fig. 1b) which is nearest to the anode. We ascribe it to the fact that the reaction (i) takes place in the vicinity of the anode due to high concentration of OH^- ions there. For the same reason, acids also show little IZ gas formation because of a dearth of OH^- ions. If the above explanation is correct we should expect a faster IZ electrolysis if one of the beakers contain water (fig. 1a) and the rest of the apparatus contains the usual KNO_3 (0.2N) solution. This is because the ion-radicals formed on the water side will have a longer life owing to a dearth of ions of opposite charge, and so they will have a better chance to migrate to the bridge tube and meet their counter-ions to liberate the IZ gas as per equation (i). Actually intermediate zone electrolysis is found to be much facilitated when the anode chamber is filled with water and the rest with the nitrate solution; for example, 5 c.c. of IZ gas is collected in 6 to 10 hours as contrasted with about 18 to 24 hours for the KNO_3 solution under comparable condition. On the other hand if the catholyte is water and the rest is the nitrate solution, the IZ gas is rather more slowly liberated under comparable conditions but as expected the IZ gas contains a much large percentage of hydrogen.

That the intermediate zone is not just a path for the ions to move but that free radicals also exist there, is conclusively proved by demonstrating the occurrence of oxidation there by the following experiment. If about half of the tube T (fig. 1a) is filled with a dilute solution of say, diphenylamine (or methyl iodide) in toluene the rest being filled with potassium nitrate solution (0.2*N*) as usual, and the current is switched on, the toluene layer assumes a yellow colour in a few hours due to oxidation of the diphenylamine (or liberation of iodine in the case of methyl iodide). Another indication that free radicals are involved is obtained from the fact on placing one of the electrodes in a strong magnetic field ($\sim 15,000$ gauss) the current reversibly diminishes, albeit slightly. This falls in line with the strong diminution of current by magnetic field during glow, as already reported by the author. Detailed results will be reported later.

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